

Influence of Product Branding on Consumers Patronage of Fast Moving Consumers Goods in Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Using Anambra State as a case study, this study examines the influence of product branding on consumers' purchases of fast-moving consumer goods. Study aims to examine the influence of perceived brand quality on consumers patronage of fast-moving consumer goods in Anambra state and to examine the influence of brand awareness on consumers patronage of fast-moving consumer goods in Anambra state We used descriptive survey design and two research questions for the study. According to the Bowley proportion formula, the study's population is made up of 640 customers, of which 320 were chosen as samples. We used primary data that was gathered through a structured survey to compile our findings. Statistical Package for Science Studies was used to analyze the data using simple percentages and test the hypotheses using linear regression (SPSS). A significant influence on the purchase of fast-moving consumer goods in Anambra state was found to be perceived brand quality. Anambra state consumers' preference for fast moving consumer goods is influenced by brand loyalty, according to the researcher. So as to increase consumption of fast-moving consumer goods in Anambra state, the researcher recommends, among other things, that manufacturing firms of fast-moving consumer goods should ensure high quality goods.

Keywords: *Influence, Product, Branding, Consumers, Patronage, Fast-Moving, Consumers, Goods*

1. Introduction

A growing number of fast-moving consumer goods are being produced around the world, in both developed and developing countries. In order to succeed in business, you must be able to anticipate customers' demands and meet them; maximize profits; maintain your competitive edge; and remain relevant in the marketplace (Lovelock & Wirtz, 2010). One of the most effective strategies for winning or overcoming competition is branding, and its effectiveness is undeniable (Williams, 2015). Customers would have to sort through a list of unbranded products in order to find the product they want, and that would take time and effort. It's possible that you'll pick the wrong product out of the many unbranded products available, given some middlemen's unscrupulous behavior. When consumers see their favorite brand (to which they may be loyal), they may cut short the analysis of alternatives prior to making a purchase decision, and proceed more quickly to make the purchase. When one realizes that branding is a marketing tool that has a direct impact on other product management decisions, one realizes that its influence on marketing activities and consumers cannot be overstated (Nnayer, 2012).

Okay (2011) captures the essence of branding by asserting that other product management decisions, such as market segmentation, promotion, product positioning, and pricing, would have been virtually impossible without branding. It seems as though consumers are bombarded with too many marketing stimuli these days. Within a 30-minute shopping session, consumers are exposed to more than 20,000 product choices, according to Keller (2013). However, companies can use branding as a tool to promote their marketing offer and increase sales. Customers can identify and differentiate products with the help of a good brand. Easy delivery and safety are two reasons why brands are used. Branding allows companies to distinguish their products from those of their competitors. It's important for companies to understand how consumers make purchasing decisions. In addition, market research helps companies determine what elements of a product's branding are important to consumers (Nnayer, 2012).

The goal of organizations, according to Alvarez and Casielles (2015), is to develop brands in order to attract and retain existing consumers. It is based on the previous information, learned reactions, and individual preferences that consumers respond to branding (Aaker, 2010). In other words, branding elements such as logos or shapes, colors, sizes, and labels can influence consumers to respond positively. As a general rule, consumers tend to evaluate certain product attributes as a whole rather than on an individual basis (Ainslie & Rossi, 2008). When trying to differentiate a company's product from that of its competitors, both extrinsic and intrinsic factors must be taken into account. As a result, brands have the potential to play a variety of roles in the consumer decision-making process.

Consumer goods that move quickly and at a low cost are known as Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG). Other non-durable items include soda, toiletries and grocery items (to name a few). Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) are generally sold in large quantities, despite the fact that their profit margins are relatively small, more so for retailers than for producers/suppliers. Probably the most classic example of a low margin/high volume business is fast-moving consumer goods (Ogwo, 2011). This industry includes both food and non-food products that are used on a daily basis by consumers. Due to the fact that they are typically purchased as the result of a small-scale consumer decision, manufacturers heavily promote them through advertising and promotion. Retail shops, kiosks, hawkers, grocery stores, and supermarkets are common places to buy these goods. Meanwhile, traditional retailers have introduced private label brands to capture additional profit from the manufacturers.

According to Moris, (2015) Fast Moving Consumer Goods are low priced and many brands and companies are involved in the manufacturing and production of same categories of products, it becomes really difficult to project a special place in the minds of the consumers. Therefore, marketers have to think of special plans and ways in which they can attract consumers towards their products even at the time of normal economic circumstances or at the time of boom in the economy. Therefore, it is against this background that this study seeks to examine the influence of product branding on consumers patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra State.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Given that Fast Moving Consumer Goods tend to be low-priced, as well as the fact that a lot of different companies are involved in manufacturing the same types of products, it is difficult to establish a unique position in the minds of buyers, according to Moris (2015). In order to attract consumers to their products, marketers need to come up with special plans and strategies, whether the economy is normal or booming. Determining the impact of product branding on consumers' purchase decisions for fast moving consumer goods in Anambra State is the purpose of this study.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the influence of product branding on consumers patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra State. Specifically, the study seeks to;

- i. Examine the influence of perceiver brand quality on consumers patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state
- ii. Examine the influence of brand awareness on consumers patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. To what extent does perceived brand quality affect consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state?
- ii. To what extent does brand awareness affect consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study

H₀₁: Perceived brand quality has no significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

H₀₂: Brand awareness has no significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Brand

An important part of marketing mix involves consumer perception of the brand (Gabor & Contiu, 2012). Customers use brands to identify and recognize goods and their manufacturer, according to Jin and Weber (2013). Individual goods were the focus of brand value creation, with firms using brands to demonstrate ownership and responsibility for their goods. In turn, customers were able to identify and recognize a company's products on sight. Companies began creating brand images in the 1930s in order to help customers distinguish one brand from another and identify the needs that a brand promises to satisfy (Jin & Weber, 2013).

2.1.2 Types of Branding

A brand can't be everything to all people at the same time. Customers will not be attracted to the same brand by definition. But branding relies on the concept of singularity, which means that it targets individuals on an individual basis. A product may have more than one of the many types of branding that are available to us today. Here are a few examples:

In the United States, the term "national brand" refers to a product that is sold under a company's own name. When it comes to any product category, the manufacturer brands are the most well-known ones. They place a high value on quality and rely heavily on advertising and sales promotion to promote their products and services (Anyanwu, 2010).

2. Private or customer brand A man, a distributor, a store, and a private individual or customer are the only ones who have access to a particular brand. Localized brand (Ehikwe, 2008). Brands such as Emphasis and others are made in Nigeria's Aba, Lagos and even the United Kingdom. Notable is that many well-known stores abroad, such as Penny and Marks & Spencer, have their clothes made in their name by other fashion houses, such as Saks Fifth Avenue (Okpara 2012). It is rare to see this kind of branding in the Nigerian market. In due course, the environment should become more favorable for private brands.

License brand: A company obtains a license from the brand owner to produce or market a brand under that license. The Tura (UK), marketed by Udeagbala Holdings, or Presidential Tailors, licensed to use Bill Blass or Gucci names on its wears (Okpara, 2012) are examples of co-branding. Through co-branding, a business can expand its brand identity and reduce costs by partnering with similar products and services. Co-branding, also known as strategic relationships, is rife on the web. Beyond content swaps, companies invite branded products and services to be sold through affiliate programs on the company's websites. If you're interested in learning more about how co-branding can help your business, contact us today! As a result of a collaboration between two brands, a product with an enhanced (or seemingly enhanced) benefit is made available.

2.1.4 Role of Branding

In the first technique of branding, the goal was to make it easier to identify and distinguish a product. After a while, brands began to embrace a promise of performance or benefit, not only for the product, but also for the company that produced it. Today, the importance of a company's brand has increased dramatically. Brands have become powerful symbols in economic, social, and political debates. In the hands of activists, brands are ideal tools because of their ability to communicate a complex message quickly and with emotional impact and their ability to attract media attention. This allows consumers to assign responsibility for the performance of the product to the manufacturer or distributor (Kotler & Keller, 2011).

As a result of past experiences with the product and its marketing programs, consumers learn which brands satisfy their needs and which ones don't. Brands also serve a useful purpose; for example, they make it easier to handle or track products. It can also be used to keep track of inventory and accounting data. It provides legal protection for the product's unique features and aspects. In order for satisfied customers to purchase the same product again, brands signal a certain level of quality to them. As an example, in Nigeria, MTN has capitalized on its brand image from its successful operations in African countries to become the leading GSM service provider in Nigeria. Example: Brand loyalty provides predictability and security of demand for the firm, and creates barriers to entry that make it difficult for new firms to enter the market. Due to Microsoft's market dominance in the software industry, other software companies have had a difficult time competing with it. As a result of customer loyalty, customers may be willing to pay a higher price, often 20 to 25% more than their competitors.

2.1.6 Consumer Preferences

To describe the factors that influence consumers' purchasing decisions, a variety of efforts and theories have been made. It is the goal of consumer behavior research to discover patterns of consumer attitudes when making a purchasing decision. It is based on Samaras (2012). When it comes to choosing a product or brand, consumers' preferences are determined by a variety of factors. Price and durability are examples of product features, while other attributes of consumers (goals, attitudes, and discretionary income) are examples of consumer attributes (Fitzsimons & Huettel, 2012).

2.1.7 Brand and Consumer Patronage

It is not uncommon for customers to opt for a brand that they believe is in line with their own self-perception. So, each consumer will try to reflect his or her identity through choice in a unique way in this way. Consumer choices tend to be similar when part of a larger social group, forming the basis of an individual's social identity (Cătălin & Andreea, 2014).

Considered an important factor in consumer decisions, brand preference involves elements of choice. Consumers compare and rank different brands by focusing on their uniqueness when establishing brand preference. When it comes to brand preference, Jin and Weber (2013) define it as "the extent to which the customer favors the designed service provided by his or her current company, in comparison to the designated service provided by other companies in his or her decision-making set," where a decision-making set refers to brands that a consumer might consider purchasing in the near future. It has also been shown that customer advice has a positive impact on the brand and consumer preferences (Güngör & Bilgin, 2011).

2.1.8 Perceived Brand quality

Qualitative judgment or perception of product superiority over other products in the same category, or close substitutes, is known as perceived quality. It is the ability of a product to offer the necessary level of satisfaction better than other alternatives. In the words of Baldauf (2013), the quality of a product is a significant resource that allows a company to achieve competitiveness. When the firm creates a brand, they need to communicate the essence of the brand with the aim of positioning it in the minds of the audience in the marketplace so as to match the characteristics of the brand to the needs and expectations of the consumers. According to Hamann (2007), branding contributes greatly to providing security and assuring customers of the quality of products. Consistently providing customers with a compelling experience leads to the development of powerful brands in a market the distribution channels, the product on offer, the physical environment, employee behavior, and brand communication all contribute to the experience. Consumers can relate to a brand because of these elements (Abimbola & Vallaster, 2007). Having a high-quality brand is not only a prerequisite to being competitive in a market; it enables also the company that owns the brand to become attractive in the marketplace. The service encounter provided by the firm to its customers serves as the strongest impression of quality of the brand; hence, every interaction between the firm and its customers affects the brand image (De Chernatony & Drury, 2006).

2.1.9 Brand Awareness

In order to build brand equity, it is necessary to create brand awareness. If consumers can recall or recognize a brand, this is an indication of how strong the brand's presence is in their minds (Aaker, 2010). A brand's equity is influenced by perceived quality, as well as brand associations. When it comes to brand associations, perceived quality refers to how consumers perceive a product's or service's overall quality or superiority (Keller & Kotler, 2011).

A brand's awareness is achieved by associating the brand with various associations in the mind (Keller & Kotler 2011). Customers must first become familiar with a brand before they can form a set of brand associations. There are several factors that influence perceptions about a particular brand (Aaker, 2010).

2.1.10 Brand loyalty

There are many different ways to define brand loyalty over the years. Product category loyalty is the practice of purchasing products from a specific product category in anticipation of their release. When choosing between two or more brands, the consumer does not take into account any marketing efforts. The emotional-physiological nature of the consumer's attachment to a specific brand is evident. Customers must be treated well in order for a company to be loyal (Aaker, 2010).

Consumers are divided into switchers, price switchers, passive loyal customers, fence sitters, and loyals, based on their level of loyalty. One of the most important things that brands need to succeed is customer loyalty. They become brand ambassadors when they become loyal to a brand and spread the word. When customers are satisfied, they will go to great lengths to promote a positive image of the brand. Relevance and meaning are the cornerstones of customer loyalty at every customer touch point. As a result, the brand's relationship with customers becomes more intimate.

A person's preferences influence their brand loyalty as well as their consumer behavior. Whatever the convenience or price, loyal customers are more likely to buy products from the brands they know and trust over others. Different marketing strategies are often used to cultivate loyal customers, such as loyalty programs (i.e. rewards programs) or trials and incentive programs (ex. samples and free gifts). Brand ambassadors are consumers who promote a certain brand and spread the word about it among their friends. Companies that are successful in cultivating loyal customers also develop brand ambassadors. A free form of word-of-mouth marketing, this is often very effective for the company's marketing efforts (Mindrut, 2015).

2.1.11 Brand Association

According to Brand Association, a consumer's positive feelings towards the brand are relatively strong. As a result of the interaction between customers and other relevant stakeholders, the brand equity of a company is affected. When customers are satisfied with a product or brand, according to some researchers, it strengthens and gains a positive reputation (Abimbola & Vallaster, 2007).

According to a study by Hamann (2007), consumers prefer and are willing to pay more for branded products when they have a choice of products in the same category. Buyers eventually identify with the brand, and they also form an emotional bond and sentimental attachment to the brand as a result of this identification. As a result of associations between the brand name and its utility or value, consumers use the brand name to make inferences about a product's quality that they are unfamiliar with.

2.1.13 Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG)

Products that are consumed on a daily basis by the average consumer and are replaced or fully used up in a short period of days, weeks, or months and within one year are considered fast moving consumer goods. CPG (Consumer Packaged Goods, or FMCG) are products that have a quick turnover and relatively low cost. It is true that FMCG products have a low profit margin, but because of their high sales volume, the total profit margin can be substantial. Products with a short shelf life are those that are in high demand or that degrade quickly. The perishability of some fast-moving consumer goods – such as meats and fruits – dairy products and baked goods – (Lovelock & Wirtz, 2010). In addition to alcohol and toiletries, other products such as pre-packaged foods, soft drinks, and cleaning products see a lot of movement.

2.1.14 Marketing Fast Moving Consumer Goods

Given that Fast Moving Consumer Goods are low-priced and a number of companies are involved in the production of the same products, it becomes increasingly difficult to establish a unique position in the minds of consumers, says Williams (2016). In order to attract consumers to their products, marketers need to come up with special plans and strategies, whether the economy is normal or booming. As a result, during a recession, the difficulties are exacerbated. It became difficult for many industries to survive because of the recent recession, which had a severe impact on the global economy. The same is true for fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG). Sellers have found it difficult to make or increase their profit margins in this low-priced and high-volume market. Due to the recession and the need to save money, people prefer to buy cheaper brands over expensive ones. As a result of the lower profit margins compared to other industries, it becomes increasingly difficult for these FMCG companies to survive and thrive. Those brands that take a proactive stance and look at the recession as an opportunity are more likely to come out of the recession stronger than they were previously.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Game Theory Developed by Neumann and Morgenstern, (1944) and Theory of Consumer Choice by Mahajan (1999)

Theory of Consumer Choice by Mahajan 1999

Mahajan's theory of consumer choice is the foundation of this research (1999). It states that consumers maximize the desirableness of their consumption as measured by their preferences subject to spending limitations and by maximizing utility subject to a consumer budget constraint, according to the theory. Consumers fully understand their own preferences, which allows for a simple but accurate comparison between any two bundles of goods presented, according to this theory's main premise All consumers want to get the most out of their purchases. Because there are two economic agents involved, consumption and production are logically separate. Immediate consumption occurs in the first case, while a producer may produce something that they do not intend to consume themselves. Maximizing utility has long been considered "rational" behavior in mainstream economics (Varian, 2006). Because of this, consumer theory revolves around generating hypotheses about the nature of consumer demand that can be refuted. When it comes to fast moving consumer goods, the importance of brand concept and consumer preferences cannot be overstated.

2.3 Empirical Review

Brand equity has a significant impact on consumer purchasing behavior in Iran, according to Masimane (2012). There were three research questions that shaped the study, and a descriptive survey design was used. 1623 people were included in the study and 322 of them were randomly selected. We used primary data that was gathered through a structured survey to compile our findings. A statistical package for social science data was used to perform multiple regression analysis on the collected data and test the hypotheses (SPSS). Brand equity has a significant impact on consumer buying behavior, according to the study.

According to Ainslie and Rossi (2008), SMEs in Nigeria have a strong sense of brand identity and reputation. There were three research questions that shaped the study, and a descriptive survey design was employed. In the study, 630 employees were involved, of which 200 were chosen at random. In this case, we were working with primary data, which was collected through a structured survey. Simple percentages were used to analyze the data, and simple linear regression was used to test the hypotheses that were generated. Brand organization has a significant impact on SME reputation, according to the findings.

Consumer purchase decisions are influenced by brand equity according to the research conducted by Matsatsinis and Samaras (2000) in Nairobi, Kenya. Three research questions guided the study, and a descriptive survey design was used. The study's population is 879 people, and 200 employees were randomly selected. The data used was a primary data collected through structured questionnaire. The data collected were analysed using percentage and the hypotheses were tested using linear regression with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS). The findings reveal that brand equity has a significant effect on consumer purchase.

Alvarez and Casielles (2015) examine the effect of Country-of-origin and brand effects on consumers' evaluations of cruise lines Kenya. The study was guided by three research questions and descriptive survey design was used. The population of the study consists of 1330 staff and 400 were sample using simple random sampling technique. The data used was a primary data collected through structured questionnaire. The data collected were analysed using simple percentage and the hypotheses were tested using simple linear regression. The findings reveal that country of origin has a significant effect on consumer evaluation.

Amegbe (2016) examine the Influence of Customer Based Brand Equity on Consumer Responses in Lagos. The study was guided by two research questions and descriptive survey design was used. The population of the study consists of 2677 staff and 399 were sample using Taro Yamen technique. In this case, we were working with primary data, which was collected through a structured survey. The data collected were analysed using percentage and the hypotheses were tested using Z-test with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS). The findings reveal that consumer based brand equity has a significant effect on consumer responses.

3. Methodology

This study will employ descriptive survey research method. This method involves the collection of data directly from the participants. Survey research is the systematic gathering of information from the participants for the purpose of understanding and/or predicting some aspect of the behavior of the study. The study is delimited to sixty-four registered supermarket selected from the three Senatorial zones in Anambra state (See appendix B). The three Senatorial zones include Anambra South, Anambra Central and Anambra North. The population of the study consists of 1600 customers that visited the 64 supermarkets. The researcher selected 25 customers each from the 64 registered supermarket (using Judgmental Sampling) who visited the supermarket to buy fast moving consumer goods thereby given a total of 1600 consumers. The selection was done using Judgmental Sampling so as to give each supermarket equal chance of participation (Source: Field Survey, 2019)

This study will be carried out in Anambra State of Nigeria. Anambra State is a state in south-South ern Nigeria in location 6.3333° N, 7.0000° E with a Land area of 4,844 km². Anambra State is bounded by Delta State in the west, Imo State in the south, Enugu State to the South and Kogi State in the north. Anambra state constitutes of twenty one local government areas with one federal university, one state university, five private university, one polytechnic and three colleges of education. Anambra people are mainly known for business.

The researcher made use of Taro Yamen's statistical formula in determining the sample size. This is shown as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

where, n = sample size, N = population size, E = error of significance, 1 = constant

Using the formula, we have

Therefore, let n? N = 1600, e = 5% or 0.05

$$n = \frac{1600}{1+1600(0.05)^2} \quad n = \frac{1600}{1+1600(0.0025)} = \frac{1600}{1+4} = \frac{1600}{5}$$

$$n = 320.$$

Bowley proportionate sampling techniques in selecting the sample size so as to assign a sample size to each supermarket. Using Bowley proportion formula, the individual sample size is obtained. The formula follows:

$$ns = \frac{N_p \times n}{N}$$

ns = the sample size allocated to each unit

Np = the population size of each unit

n = the total sample size

N = the total population size

Calculation for each sample size

$$ns = \frac{25 \times 320}{1600} = 5 \text{ for each sample size.}$$

Therefore, the sample size for the study is $64 \times 5 = 320$ customers (see appendix II for distribution)

The data used in this research study was primary data collected through structural questionnaire. The questionnaire which was designed to address the research question, adopts the close form. It consisted of two sections; the demographic information section and the general question on the research topic. The questionnaire is based on the five (5) point scale that is Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UN), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). To ensure the validity of the questionnaire, the questionnaire together with the objective of the study and hypotheses were sent to two experts and specialists in the field of research at Faculties of Management Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. This was to establish that the instrument was the appropriate one for measuring the variables contained in the study. The instrument was judged to have both face and content validity. The opinions and advice of these experts and specialists were highly considered in preparation of the final draft of the questionnaire.

The researcher will personally visit the supermarket with the copies of the questionnaire, which were administered to the consumers with the help of research assistants. Copies of the questionnaire were filled by the consumers and collected back immediately. This is to ensure high percentage of returned questionnaire.

To ensure that the instrument will be able to elicit consistent result, it was tested for internal consistency using Cronbach's Alpha test. The pilot study was conducted using twenty five percent (25%) of the sample size of the study which is eighty (80) copies of questionnaire. At the end, sixty seven (67) copies were retrieved representing twenty one percent (21%) of the sample size. The result obtained is shown in the table below:

Table 3.1 Reliability Statistic

Cronbach's Alpha	N. of items
.79	67

Source: Field Survey (pilot Study), 2021

Computation: SPSS ver. 23

From the result obtained, the reliability coefficient was .79 which if converted into percentage is 79%. This signifies that the instrument is reliable and capable of eliciting consistent result.

In analyzing the data, frequency and percentage were employed. Simple linear regression was used to test the hypotheses.

Decision Rule: we do not reject the alternative hypothesis when the probability value is less than alpha otherwise reject.

4. Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

This chapter deals with presentation and analysis of data based on the hypotheses stated in the study.

Table 4.1 Distribution of the Respondents on brand awareness

S/N	Items on brand awareness	SA	A	D	SD	U	Total
1	As a customer am attracted to brand due to its awareness	200(67%)	67(23%)	10(3%)	15(5%)	5(2%)	297(100%)
2	I patronise a particular product as a result of full knowledge about the brand	147(50%)	108(36%)	22(7%)	16(5%)	4(1%)	297(100%)
3	I buy voluminously as a result of my conviction through brand awareness	160(54%)	98(33%)	28(9%)	7(2%)	4(1%)	297(100%)
4	I change my buying decision as a result of brand awareness	60(20%)	200(67%)	5(1%)	28(9%)	5(2%)	297(100%)
5	As a customer i introduce my friends to a good brand which am aware of.	155(52%)	88(30%)	42(14%)	12(4%)		297(100%)

In Table 4.7, it's clear that 67 percent of respondents strongly agreed that as a customer, they are attracted to a brand because of its awareness, while 23 percent agreed, 3% disagreed, 5% strongly disagreed, and 2% were undecided.

When asked if they patronize a particular brand because of their knowledge of it, 50 percent of respondents strongly agreed; 36% agreed; 7% disagreed strongly; and 5% were undecided.

As for brand awareness, 54 percent of respondents strongly agree, 33 percent disagree, 2 percent strongly disagree, and 1 percent are undecided.

After the analysis was completed, 20 percent of respondents strongly agreed that they changed their buying decision as a result of brand awareness.

There are 52 percent of respondents strongly agreeing with the statement that they introduce their friends to a good brand they are aware of as a customer.

Table 4.2 Distribution of the Respondents on brand loyalty

	Items on brand loyalty	SA	A	D	SD	U	Total
12	I stick to my brand even when the cost increases	97(33%)	123(41%)	33(11%)	35(12%)	9(3%)	297(100%)
13	I introduce my friends to a particular product as a result of brand loyalty	99(33%)	167(56%)	23(8%)	8(3%)		297(100%)
14	I cannot be influence by friends even when they have contrary view about my brand	89(30%)	143(48%)	25(8%)	33(11%)	7(2%)	297(100%)
15	I exercise patience to get my brad even on stock out	98(33%)	144(49%)	29(10%)	16(5%)	10(3%)	297(100%)
16	I can continuously use a particular brand once it satisfies my need	108(36%)	139(47%)	33(11%)	17(6%)		297(100%)

From the analysis in Table 4.2 above, it is clear that 33 of the respondents strongly agreed that they would stick with their brand even if the cost went up.

Thirty-three percent (33%) of respondents strongly agreed that they would introduce their friends to a particular product as a result of their brand loyalty.

This analysis shows that 30% of respondents strongly agree that they cannot be influenced by friends, even when they have opposing views on their brand.

According to the above analysis, 33 percent of respondents strongly agreed that they exercise patience to get their brand even on stock out, 49 percent agreed, 10 percent disagreed, 5 percent strongly disagreed, and 3 percent were undecided.

This analysis shows that 36 percent of respondents strongly agreed that they can continue to use a particular brand once it meets their needs. Of the respondents who agreed with this statement, 47 percent agreed with it, 11 percent disagreed, and 6 percent strongly disagreed.

4.2 Test of Hypothesis Using Statistical Package for Social Science (Spss, 23)

Decision rule: We accept the null hypothesis when the probability value is greater than the alpha value, otherwise we reject it.

Hypothesis I

H₀₁: Perceived brand quality has no significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

H₁: Perceived brand quality has a significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-3.595	64.912		-.055	.001
	Perceived brand quality	1.365	2.570	.293	.531	.002

a. Dependent Variable: consumer patronage

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.570	1	27.570	.112	.004
	Residual	293.230	3	97.743		
	Total	320.800	4			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived brand quality

b. Dependent Variable: consumer patronage

consumer patronage = -3.595+ 1.365 perceive brand quality.

This shows that for every unit increase in perceived brand quality, consumer patronage increases by 1.365.

From the analysis above, it shows that the probability value (0.004) is less than the alpha value (0.05), the researcher accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that Perceived brand quality has a significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state.

Hypothesis II

H₀: Brand awareness has no significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

H₁: Brand awareness has a significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	70.100	1	70.100	.439	.002 ^a
	Residual	478.700	3	159.567		
	Total	548.800	4			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand awareness

b. Dependent Variable: consumer patronage

Coefficients^a

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	70.100	1	70.100	.439	.002 ^a
	Residual	478.700	3	159.567		
	Total	548.800	4			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand awareness

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	87.861	42.113		2.086	.008
	Brand awareness	.499	.753	.357	.663	.000

a. Dependent Variable: consumer patronage

From the analysis above the model is give as below

consumer patronage = 87.861 + 0.499 brand awareness.

This shows that for every unit increase in brand awareness, consumer patronage increases by 0.499.

From the analysis above, it shows that the probability value (0.0021) is less than the alpha value (0.05), the researcher accepts the alternative hypothesis and conclude that brand awareness has a significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

Summary of Findings

From the discussion of findings, the summary was made

1. Perceived brand quality has no significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

(P-value =0.004<0.05)

2. Brand awareness has no significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state.

(P-value =0.0021<0.05)

5. Conclusion

From the discussion of findings, the researcher concluded that perceived brand quality has a significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state, brand awareness has a significant influence a consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state and that brand association has a significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state. This shows that brand loyalty has a significant influence on consumers' patronage of fast-moving consumer goods in Anambra state.

Recommendations

Having discussed the findings and drawn some conclusions therein, the following recommendations were made;

1. Manufacturing firms of fast moving consumer goods should ensure high quality goods so as to increase consumers patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

2. Manufacturing firms of fast moving consumer goods should intensify effort towards brand awareness so as to increase consumers patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

3. Supermarket should ensure that the fast moving consumer goods which they purchase for retail has a positive brand association so as to increases consumer patronage of fast moving consumer goods in Anambra state

Contribution to Knowledge

This study is among the first contribution in the area of product branding within the context of consumers patronage of fast moving consumers goods in Anambra State. This study contributed to the body of knowledge by building a concept that integrated product branding as it relates to consumers patronage.

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